

3. Gilmore, A. (2007). Authentic materials and authenticity in foreign language learning. *Language Teaching*, 40(2), 97–118.
4. Larsen-Freeman, D. (2000). *Techniques and principles in language teaching* (2nd ed.). Oxford University Press.
5. Brown, H. D. (2007). *Principles of Language Learning and Teaching* (5th ed.). Pearson Education.

THE RELEVANCE OF INTERCULTURAL RELATIONS

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***Abstract.** This paper explains the role of intercultural relationships within the translation process. Such as, in increasing interaction with different cultures, and improving both financial and cultural ties. The study highlights the necessity of accounting for cultural differences through tasks, including the translation of realia, idiomatic expressions, proverbs, and religious terms.*

***Keywords.** Intercultural relations, cultural barriers, ethnocentrism, mechanization of communications, adaptation, idioms, proverbs.*

Introduction. In today's developed era, intercultural relations are spreading rapidly. Each nation began to show its skills and abilities to the world market. Every day, they try themselves in every aspect of the international arena and record international achievements. Especially today's young people are able to express themselves in many fields. The latest developments of today's developed era are strengthened by international exchange relations. These expressions often carry meanings deeply rooted in the source of culture, making literal translation insufficient or even misleading. Translators must navigate the complex interplay between preserving the authenticity of the source text and ensuring its accessibility to the target audience.

Evaluating cross-cultural communication

The originator of the communication strategy's prior intercultural communication expertise has to be impartially evaluated. This evaluation of intercultural communication has to look at the organization's level of expertise as well as the effectiveness of its previous interactions with different partners from other nations and cultures. Essentially, a person's proficiency in intercultural communication is determined by their range of skills and knowledge, which are mostly derived via creating meaningful and impactful cross-cultural communications.. Through translation, cultures emphasize the interconnectedness of the world community and demonstrate the improvement of mutual respect. Today, various fields connect us with other countries, for example, continuous communication, medicine, literature, business and management, politics and diplomatic relations. If we know that each country has its own national wealth, the culture and language concepts of each country are complex. And every country wants to have a common language to improve seamless communication with other countries.

Cultural barriers. Joynt & Warner said that: “Culture is the pattern of taken-for-granted assumptions about how a given collection of people should think, act, and feel as they go about their daily affairs” Culture is all socially transmitted behavior, arts, architectures, languages, signs, symbols, ideas, beliefs, norms, traditions, rituals, etc. which is learnt and shared in a particular social group of the same nationality, ethnicity, religion.

Ethnocentrism. Ethnocentrism is the process of dividing cultures as “us” and “them”. The people of someone’s own culture are categorised as in-group and the other culture is out-group. There is always a greater preference for in-group. There is an illusion of the out-group as evil and inferior. This evaluation is mostly negative.

In short, translation today includes not only developed countries, but also developing and underdeveloped countries. The national tradition between them

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also implements the exchange of customs, values and inventions and discoveries. At the same time, the translation preserves its uniqueness in reflecting the richness of intercultural relations. We can have no doubt that translation will find its place in every field and it will also rank high in educational news. We can see that through this translation, ancient fossils and monuments can introduce the country to the world and be an important innovation between cultures. Nowadays, as translation has found its place in many fields, foreign countries also prioritize translation in to present their national and modern values.

REFERENCES

1. Hofstede, G. (2001). *Culture's Consequences: Comparing Values, Behaviors, Institutions, and Organizations Across Nations*. SAGE Publications.
2. Ting-Toomey, S. (1999). *Communicating Across Cultures*. Guilford Press.
3. Samovar, L. A., Porter, R. E., McDaniel, E. R., & Roy, C. S. (2017). *Communication Between Cultures*. Cengage Learning.
4. Kim, Y. Y. (2001). *Becoming Intercultural: An Integrative Theory of Communication and Cross-Cultural Adaptation*. SAGE Publications
5. Trompenaars, F., & Hampden-Turner, C. (2012). *Riding the Waves of Culture: Understanding Diversity in Global Business*. Nicholas Brealey Publishing.
6. Gudykunst, W. B., & Kim, Y. Y. (2003). *Communicating with Strangers: An Approach to Intercultural Communication*. McGraw-Hill Education.

INCLUSIVE STRATEGIES FOR MIDDLE SCHOOL LANGUAGE TEACHING WITH DIGITAL TOOLS

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